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Research Paper

EFFICACY OF *Annona squamosa* (CUSTARD APPLE), *Azadirachta indica* (NEEM), AND *Dracaena arborea* LEAVES EXTRACTS ON COCKROACHES (*Periplaneta americana*)

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Abstract

Cockroaches, particularly *Periplaneta americana*, are a major concern in public health and hygiene. The use of synthetic pesticides has resulted in the development of resistance in these insects. Therefore, alternative methods, such as natural plant extracts, have been investigated as potential cockroach control agents. This study aimed to evaluate the efficacy of different plant extracts, including *Annona squamosa*, *Azadirachta indica* and *Dracaena arborea* against *P. americana*. The extracts were tested for their insecticidal activity by exposing the cockroaches to the extract solutions in a bioassay. The study involved three treatment groups with varying concentrations of leaf extract (100ml, 50ml). Each group consisted of 30 cockroaches, and there were 3 replications for each treatment. One control is also added and there are 3 replicas of control. The number of mortalities (%) after treatment was calculated and analyzed using one-way ANOVA. The leaf extracts at concentrations of 50ml and 100ml were effective in killing *Periplaneta americana*. 100ml ethanolic concentration of leave extract of *Azadirachta indica* shows highest average mortality % of Cockroaches (mean±SE) is 96.6±0.33. There are significant differences between the Research groups (F calculated 70.53 >F table 54.815> F table 40.16).

Key words: Leaf extract, bioactive Chemicals, Efficacy, Mortality and Cockroaches.

INTRODUCTION

Periplaneta americana, also known as the American cockroach, is a species of cockroach that is found in many parts of the world, including North America, South America, Asia, Africa, and Australia. Some important general features about cockroaches, including *P. americana*, they are commonly found indoors, particularly in areas with food and water sources, such as kitchens, bathrooms, and basements. They prefer warm, humid

environments and can thrive in cracks and crevices, under appliances and furniture, and in wall voids. Cockroaches also live in outdoor environments such as gardens, sewers, and garbage dumps. Some species of cockroaches, such as the Oriental cockroach, are commonly found outdoors and can enter homes through cracks and openings.

Cockroaches, including *P. americana*, can be a health hazard, as they can carry bacteria, viruses, and other pathogens that can be harmful to humans. They can also cause allergies and asthma in some people [9].

Indigenous plants naturally occur in nature, especially in tropical regions, and are often associated with various domestic uses. These plants contain bioactive Chemicals, which serve as suitable alternative Biocontrol substances. Thus, leaves, roots, flowers, fruits, seeds, cloves, Rhizomes and stems. The plant parts are dried and finely powdered before being subjected to extraction using organic solvents to optimize the extraction of the desired compounds. Subsequently, the extracts are concentrated, formulated, and subjected to evaluation for efficacy under laboratory, controlled Or field conditions [2].

Over two hundred plants, including neem, with insecticidal properties have demonstrated success in controlling more than five hundred and fifty insect species belonging to the orders Dictyoptera, which encompass cockroaches and mantises, Coleoptera, Isoptera, Homoptera, Heteroptera, Diptera, Orthoptera and others [8, 4].

PLANTS USE FOR EXTRACTION OF LEAVES EXTRACT

A. *Annona squamosa* (Custard apple)- *Annona squamosa*, commonly known as sugar apple or custard apple, is a tropical fruit-bearing tree. *Annona squamosa* leaves have been traditionally used in various medicinal preparations due to their potential therapeutic properties [13]. *Annona squamosa* leaves may contain bioactive compounds that could potentially have insecticidal properties, further research is needed to evaluate their efficacy specifically against cockroaches (Plate -1).

B. *Azadirachta indica* (Neem)- Neem leaves (*Azadirachta indica*) have long been used in traditional medicine and pest control due to their natural insecticidal properties. Neem leaves contain several compounds, including azadirachtin, which is known to have insecticidal effects [10]. The extract can disrupt the growth and development of cockroaches, affecting their reproductive capabilities and causing mortality (Plate -1).

C. *Dracaena arborea* (Gambhari tree)- *Dracaena arborea*, also known as the Dragon Tree, is a plant species that belongs to the Asparagaceae family. While this plant has several traditional uses [11]. Some studies have reported the presence of bioactive compounds in *Dracaena* plants with potential insecticidal properties [7]. These compounds may exhibit antiparasitic, antifungal, and insecticidal activities [17] (Plate-1).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The subjects for the experiment will be adult cockroaches obtained from households. Due to the extended life cycle of cockroaches, it was not possible to homogenize the subjects through laboratory rearing. Therefore, the study will randomly select adult cockroaches with similar sizes (35-40 cm) The sampling process will be conducted randomly to ensure unbiased selection of adult *Periplaneta americana* cockroaches. The random selection will help to minimize any potential confounding factors that may influence the outcomes. Adult *Periplaneta americana* cockroaches are characterized by their reddish-brown color, with pale brown or yellow bands on the pronotum's corners. These cockroaches are commonly found in household environments.

COLLECTION OF PLANT LEAVES

Collection of leaves of *Annona squamosa*, *Azadirachta indica*, *Dracaena arborea* were collected from the Department of Zoology & Department of Nutrition, Isabella Thoburn College, Lucknow, India (Plate-1).

Plate 1 Plants used for experiment

S.No.	Common name	Botanical name	Plants use for extraction of leaves extract
1.	Custard apple	<i>Annona squamosa</i>	

2.	Neem	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	
3.	Gambhari tree	<i>Dracaena arborea</i>	

THE INSTRUMENTS USED IN EXPERIMENTS

Boxes measuring 20 cm in length and 5 cm in diameter, equipped with covers. These boxes contained 50 holes with a diameter of 20 mm to allow for cockroach respiration. Additionally, tweezers, filter paper, and a timer were employed. The materials used included the ethanol extract of, *Annona squamosa*, *Azadirachta indica* and *Dracaena arborea* leaves, ethanol, and distilled water.

PREPARATION OF LEAVES EXTRACTS

Leaves of *Annona squamosa*, *Azadirachta indica*, and *Dracaena arborea* were collected from plants and air-dried. The dried leaves were then powdered. A total of 15 g of the powdered material was soaked in a glass jar for 24 hours in a solution consisting of 15 ml of water and 50 ml of ethanol as the solvent. Afterward, the solutions were filtered through a filter, and the resulting extracts were stored in the refrigerator at 4°C before being used. [5,15].

The research variables involve the concentrations of *Annona squamosa*, *Azadirachta indica* and *Dracaena arborea* leaf extract as the independent variable and cockroach

mortality (%) as the dependent variable. Two concentrations of the extracts, namely 50 ml and 100 ml, will be tested. Cockroach mortality is defined as the percentage of dead subjects out of the total number of subjects multiplied by 100%. To establish a comparison, a control group exposed to (distilled water) was used.

EXPERIMENTATION

Based on the method used by Udo (2008b) plastic boxes were prepared with Whatman No. 1 filter paper. Two different volumes, 50 ml and 100 ml, of ethanolic leaf extracts were applied to separate boxes and allowed to dry for thirty minutes. Each box was randomly populated with ten adult insects. A control group was treated with distilled water, and each treatment was replicated three times. Insects were observed and recorded daily for mortality within 24, 48, and 72 hours. Any insect that remained immobile and unresponsive to three probing attempts with a blunt dissecting probe during a five-minute recovery period was considered dead.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The statistical analysis of data was done, calculated the mean and standard error (Mean±SE) of data. Data were submitted to one way ANOVA using SPSS software. When the ANOVA statistics were significant ($p \leq 0.001$), the mean separation was performed by Dunnett multiple range test [16].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Botanical pesticides indeed play a significant role in integrated pest management (IPM) systems for traditional pest control. They offer several advantages, including their broad-spectrum action, utilization of local materials, and potential cost-effectiveness [5]. Results of statistical tests with one way ANOVA shows that there are significant Differences between the research groups (F calculated 70.53 $> F$ table 54.815 $> F$ table 40.16). The mean separation was performed by Dunnett multiple range test. that in research groups on *Annona Squamosa*, *Azadirachta indica*, *Dracaena arborea* leaf leaves extract concentration Treatment group on extracts 50ml, 100ml proven effective killing *Periplaneta Americana* in comparison to control group [16]. Direct contact between the toxicants or active ingredients presents in the test plants and the bodies of insects contributed to the mortality of adult insects. When insects came into direct contact with these substances, it resulted in harmful effects that led to their death [3, 1, 6, 12].

Annona squamosa: The mortality of cockroaches after 50ml concentration of *Annona squamosa* Leaves extract (mean \pm SE) for 24 hrs. are 2.33 ± 0.33 , for 100ml (mean \pm SE) is 5.00 ± 0.57 for 24hrs of exposure. For 48hr of exposure of 50ml concentration of *Annona squamosa* the mortality (mean \pm SE) is 4.33 ± 0.33 and for 100ml concentration the mortality (mean \pm SE) is 7.33 ± 0.33 . And in 72 hrs. of exposure of 50 ml of concentration of *Annona squamosa* the mortality of cockroaches (mean \pm SE) is 4.66 ± 0.33 , and for 100ml exposure the concentration of 100ml of *Annona squamosa* the mortality of cockroaches (mean \pm SE) is 8.66 ± 0.33 (Table-1 and Fig.1).

Azadirachta indica: The mortality of cockroaches after treatment of 50ml concentration of *Azadirachta indica* leaves extract for 24 hrs. are (mean \pm SE) 5.66 ± 0.33 , for 100ml concentration of *Azadirachta* leaves extract for exposure of 24hrs are (mean \pm SE) 7.66 ± 0.33 . The exposure of 50 ml *Azadirachta* leaves extract for 48 hrs. The mortality of cockroaches is (mean \pm SE) 5.66 ± 0.33 , and for the concentration of 100ml at 48 hrs. exposure the mortality of cockroaches is (mean \pm SE) 8.66 ± 0.33 . The 50ml concentration of *Azadirachta* leaves extract for 72 hrs. causes mortality of cockroaches (mean \pm SE) are 6.33 ± 0.33 . The mortality of cockroaches is highest in the 72 hrs. exposure at 100 ml *Azadirachta* extract is (mean \pm SE) 9.66 ± 0.33 (Table-1 and Fig.1).

Dracaena arborea: The mortality of cockroaches after treatment with 50ml leaves extract of *Dracaena arborea* for 24 hrs. are (mean \pm SE) 3.66 ± 0.33 , and the mortality causes by 100 ml concentration of *Dracaena arborea* for 24 hrs. are (mean \pm SE) 5.66 ± 0.33 . For 48 hrs. treatment we took again two concentration 50ml and 100ml, 50ml causes mortality of cockroaches (mean \pm SE) 4.00 ± 0.00 and 100 ml leave extract causes mortality of (mean \pm SE) 6.66 ± 0.33 cockroaches. For 72 hrs. treatment the mortality causes by 50ml of *Dracaena* leaves extract are (mean \pm SE) 4.00 ± 5.77 and for 100 ml mortality of cockroaches were recorded (mean \pm SE) 7.33 ± 0.33 (Table-1 and Fig.1).

The mortality of Cockroaches recorded in control group were (mean \pm SE) 1.00 ± 0.00 for 24 hrs. of exposure for 48 hrs. of exposure the (mean \pm SE) is also 1.00 ± 0.00 and for 72 hrs. of exposure the mortality of Cockroaches recorded were (mean \pm SE) 1.66 ± 0.3 (Table-1 and Fig.1).

Table 1 : Shows the mortality (Mean±SE) of Cockroaches after treatment and Average Mortality % (Mean±SE) of Cockroaches.

Leaf Extracts	No. of Cockroaches introduced in each replica	Doses in ml	Mortality (mean± S.E) of Cockroaches after treatment application			Average mortality % (mean±S.E) of Cockroaches)		
			24hr (day1)	48hr (day2)	72hr (day3)	24hr (day1)	48hr (day2)	72hr (day3)
<i>Annona squamosa</i>	10	50ml	2.33±0.33	4.33±0.33	4.66±0.33	23.3±0.33	43.3±0.33	46.6±0.33
	10	100ml	5.00±0.57	7.33±0.33	8.66±0.33	50±0.57	73.3±0.33	86.6±0.33
<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	10	50ml	5.66±0.33	5.66±0.33	6.33±0.33	56.6±0.33	56.6±0.33	63.3±0.33
	10	100ml	7.66±0.33	8.33±0.33	9.66±0.33	76.6±0.33	83.3±0.33	96.6±0.33
<i>D. arborea</i>	10	50ml	3.66±0.33	4.00±0.00	4.00±5.77	36.6±0.33	40±0.00	40.0±5.77
	10	100ml	5.66±0.33	6.66±0.33	7.33±0.33	56.6±0.33	66.6±0.33	73.3±0.33
Control	10		1.00±0.00	1.00±0.00	1.66±0.33	10±0.00	10±0.00	16.6±0.33

Fig-1- Mean Mortality of Cockroaches due to effect of leaves extracts

CONCLUSION

The ethanolic extract derived from the leaves of *Annona squamosa*, *Azadirachta indica*, and *Dracaena arborea* shows promise as a potential insecticide for controlling cockroaches through direct contact. Although each of these plant extracts individually has been studied for their insecticidal properties [1].

Azadirachta indica, commonly known as neem, is renowned for its insecticidal properties. It has been extensively researched and proven to have strong insecticidal effects on various pests, including cockroaches. The ethanolic extract derived from neem leaves has shown the highest mortality rate among the tested plant extracts when

compared to a control group. This suggests that neem extract could be particularly effective in controlling cockroach populations.

Annona squamosa, or custard apple, and *Dracaena arborea* have also been investigated for their potential insecticidal activity. While they may not exhibit the same level of efficacy as neem, these plants still possess bioactive compounds that contribute to their insecticidal properties. These compounds can act as natural pesticides, disrupting the physiology or behavior of pests and leading to their death.

The use of plant extracts as insecticides offers several advantages. Firstly, they are derived from natural sources, which may be preferable for those seeking environmentally friendly alternatives to synthetic chemicals. Additionally, these plant extracts often have low toxicity to mammals, including humans, making them safer to use in domestic or agricultural settings. However, it is essential to ensure that the concentrations and application methods are appropriate to maximize their effectiveness while minimizing any potential harm to non-target organisms.

In conclusion, the ethanolic extracts from *Annona squamosa*, *Azadirachta indica*, and *Dracaena arborea* show promise as potential insecticides for controlling cockroaches through direct contact. Neem extract, in particular, has demonstrated high efficacy, while custard apple and *Dracaena arborea* extracts also exhibit insecticidal activity. Further research and optimization of these plant extracts could lead to the development of effective and environmentally friendly Cockroach repellent.

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REFERENCES

1. Echendu, TN C. 1991 "Ginger, cashew and neem as surface protectants of cowpeas against infestation and damage by *Callosobruchus maculatus* (Fab.)." *Tropical science* 31.2: 209-211.
2. Kassie W.B. 2020. Evaluating the effect of three plant leaf extract against German cockroach (*Blattella germanica*) survival under uncontrolled condition, *Int. J. of Pharm. & Life Sci.*, 11(8): 6921- 6926.
3. Lajide, L.; Adedire, C. O.; Muse, W. A.; Agele, S. O. 1998. Insecticidal activity of powders of some Nigerian plants against the maize weevil (*Sitophilus zeamais* Motsch). In Lale, N. E. S.; Molta, N. B.; Donli, P. O.; Dike, M. C.; Aminu-Kano, M.

- (Editors) Entomology in the Nigerian economy. Research focus in the 21st century, Entomological Society of Nigeria Occasional Publication 31: 227-235. (Tetrapleura tetraptera, Uvaria afzelli, Vernonia amygdalina)
4. Mordue Anne Jennifer and Nisbet Alasdair J 2000. Azadirachtin from the neem tree *Azadirachta indica*: Its action against insects Anais da Sociedade Entomológica do Brasil 29(4):615-632
 5. Obeng-Ofori, D., Reichmuth, C.H., Bekele, J. and Hassanali, A., 1997. Biological activity of 1, 8 cineole, a major component of essential oil of *Ocimum kenyense* (Ayobangira) against stored product beetles. Journal of Applied Entomology, 121(1-5), pp.237-243.
 6. Okonkwo, E. U., and W. I. Okoye 1996. "The efficacy of four seed powders and the essential oils as protectants of cowpea and maize grains against infestation by *Callosobruchus maculatus* (Fabricus)(Coleoptera: Bruchidae) and *Sitophilus zeamais* (Motschulsky)(Coleoptera: Curculionidae) in Nigeria." *International Journal of Pest Management* 42.3: 143-146.
 7. Okwu D. E. 2001 "Evaluation of the chemical composition of Indigenous Spices and Flavouring Agents," Global Journal of Pure and Applied Science, vol. 7, pp. 455-459.
 8. Saleh Al-Quraishy and Fathy A. Abdel-Ghaffar and Khaled A. S. Al-Rasheid and Julia Mehlhorn and Heinz Mehlhorn 2011. Effects of a neem seed extract (MiteStop®) on mallophages (featherlings) of chicken: in vivo and in vitro studies. Parasitology Research, Volume 110, pp 617 - 622
 9. Sarinho, E., Schor, D., Veloso, M. A., & Rizzo, J. A. 2004. There are more asthmatics in homes with high cockroach infestation. Brazilian journal of medical and biological research, 37(4), 503-510.
 10. Schmutterer, H. 1990 "Properties and potential of natural pesticides from the neem tree, *Azadirachta indica*." Annual review of entomology 35.1 (1990): 271-297.
 11. Senthil, N. S., & Kalaivani, K. 2005. Efficacy of Nucleo polyhedron virus (NPV) and Azadirachtin on *Spodoptera littura* Fabricius (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae). Biological Control, 34, 93-98.

12. Shaaya, E., Ravid, U., Paster, N., Juven, B., Zisman, U., & Pissarev, V. 1991. Fumigant toxicity of essential oils against four major stored-product insects. *Journal of chemical ecology*, 17, 499-504.
13. T Kesetyaningsih W 2012. Efficacy of *Annona squamosa* Leaf Extract as An Insecticide against Cockroach (*Periplaneta americana*).
14. Udo, I. O. 2008b. Efficacy of plant parts of Dragon and Wood-oil-nut trees against maize weevil (*Sitophilus zeamais* Motsch.) and cowpea weevil (*Callosobruchus maculatus* F.) Ph D Thesis, Rivers State University of Science and Technology.
15. Udo, I. O. 2013. Phytochemical screening of *Dracaena arborea* (Asparagaceae) for insecticidal Activity in the control of *Sitophilus zeamais* (Coleoptera: Curculionidae) and *Callosobruchus Maculatus* (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae). *International journal of tropical Insect science*, 33(2), 136-143.
16. Ukoroije, Rosemary Boate, and Rosetta Bekinwari Bobmanuel 2019. "Insecticidal activity of leaf powder and ethanolic extracts of *Azadirachta indica*, *Ocimum gratissimum* and *Dracaena arborea* against nymphs of the domestic pest *Periplaneta americana* (Dictyoptera: Blatellidae)." *Noble International Journal of Scientific Research* 3.12: 117-135.
17. Umar, H. T. Abdulraliman, and M. Kokori 2002. "Preliminary studies of the efficacy of the aqueous Extracts of leaf and seed kernel of *A. indica* (*A. indica* Juss) for the control of cowpea Bruchid, *Callosobruchus maculatus* (Coleoptera: Bruchidae)," *Research Journal of Science*, vol. 8, pp. 25-30.